

1st Year Progress Report

Jeffrey M. Ede

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PhD Topic: Application of Novel Computing and Data Analysis Methods in Electron Microscopy

1 Foreword

The first few months of my PhD have been focused on the development of key computational skills that will be needed throughout the rest of my PhD. Specifically, I have been completing a variety of tasks that apply computer vision[1, 2], machine learning; particularly deep learning[3], heterogeneous computational acceleration[4] using multithreading[5] and graphical processing units[6–8] (GPUs) and other skills to the electron microscopy of nanomaterials. This has necessarily involved learning to write scripts to automate electron microscope procedures and implementing remote control protocols and interfaces so that our electron microscopes can be remote-controlled by neural networks.

The bulk of this report has been structured into a series of short sections that briefly describe a task, the skills developed by doing it and then provide an extended description. This is followed by a summary of some key programming libraries I have learned to use, a summary of MPAGS and year 1 doctoral skills tasks I have completed, a brief outline of the direction of my PhD and then 5 key text summaries.

2 Skill Development

This section describes some of the tasks I have completed to develop key computational skills and become familiar with programming electron microscopes. Some of the source code written to perform these tasks has been published and may be reused freely, subject to its license:

<https://github.com/Jeffrey-Ede/Beanland-Atlas>

Task: Convolution-based digital large angle convergent beam electron diffraction[9] (D-LACBED) disk position extraction

Skills: GPU-accelerated Fourier analysis[10–12], Overconstrained system of simultaneous equations

Description: The positions of LACBED pattern disks and the patterns in them vary as an electron microscope specimen is tilted relative to a converging electron beam. Disk patterns differ in different images and often either partially or completely obscures the disks by reducing portions of the disks' intensities to that of the surrounding background. The situation is complicated further by disk shapes and positions changing as they sweep through aberrating fields. To get an initial estimate of the disk positions, the following procedure has been implemented:

1. Estimate LACBED disk sizes by GPU-accelerating the convolution of images' Sobel filtrates with annular kernels of various sizes. Annulus weights were uniform and scaled to sum to 1.0 so that the convolution producing the highest-values output pixel would be that where the disk size is approximately the same as that of the annulus. This follows because the annular kernel is an even function so the convolution is the same as a cross-correlation.
2. GPU-accelerate the convolution of the images with circular kernels and their Sobel filtrate amplitudes with the annular kernels that are the size of the disks and then multiply these convolutions together. Sobel components were summed in quadrature rather than directory as accuracy was considered

Figure 1: a) A large angle convergent beam electron diffraction (LACBED) pattern and b) the amplitude of its gradient. This gradient was calculated by convolving the LACBED pattern with orthogonal Scharr [13, 14] kernels and Hadamard summing the resulting filtrates in quadrature, rather than by direct addition. c) Multiplying the cross-correlation of the LACBED pattern with a LACBED disk-sized circle with the cross-correlation of its gradient with a LACBED disk-sized annulus creates a space where disk positions are marked by local maxima. Brighter disks with higher-gradient, clearer dark region-to-disk transitions have higher maxima.

more important than the increased computational time as gradation was often broken by dynamical diffraction effects. Nevertheless, direct addition was found to not significantly decrease performance in practice. The convolution with the Sobel filtrate has high values where the annular kernel is positioned over the disks as there is high gradation at the edges of the disks. Nevertheless, this is not enough to reliably reveal their positions as disk patterns change the gradation, sometimes removing it completely. Consequently, micrographs were also convolved with circles to reveal the regions of high brightness: the disks. By multiplying the edge and brightness based disk-position-revealing convolutions a better estimate for the disk positions is calculated. An alternative procedure based on recursive convolution of the Sobel filtrates with annuluses was also developed for the high spot separation limit.

3. Phase correlate the convolution products of the previous step to reveal the relative positions of the disks in different images
4. Shift the positions of the images so that the disk positions would all be the same in the absence of aberrating fields. By summing these images together to create an aligned image, the disk patterns are averaged out; at least, to the extent that there is a bright region where each of the spots are.
5. Convolve the aligned image with a circular kernel to reveal the positions of these bright regions. Systematically detect the brightest pixel and then black the region around that pixel in the convolution out to detect the disks. Repeat this until the number of spots for square packing; the least dense packing, are detected.
6. Determine the diffraction spot packing using the number of spots approximately equidistant from the brightest spot in the aligned spot pattern.
7. Construct an overconstrained system of simultaneous equations from the spot positions and solve it to find the diffraction pattern lattice vectors.
8. Use the lattice vectors to identify and correct any anomalous positions.
9. The positions of the spots in the aligned pattern and the relative positions of the images to the aligned pattern are then all known so the position of the disks in each image are then known, regardless of how much they are obscured by the patterns within them.

Figure 2: Automatically constructed digital large angle convergent beam electron diffraction pattern (D-LACBED) for silicon showing dynamical diffraction effects with 4mm overall symmetry. k-space surveys mapped out by LACBED disks have been placed on a black image and separated in proportion to separations calculated from an initial estimates of the disk positions. Outer surveys are smaller as they are cut off for specimen tilts that moved their surveying LACBED disks off the camera.

Note that this algorithm was designed so that I could practice GPU-accelerated Fourier analysis. A more appropriate algorithm that can identify additional disk parameters; such as characteristics of the disks' motion, using GPU-accelerated neural networks is now being developed.

Task: Aberration commensuration by style transfer

Skills: Transfer deep learning [15, 16], Convolutional neural networks [17, 18], Loss networks[19]

Description: To the best of my knowledge, there is no method that can directly average or combine 2 images with the same content that are subject to different aberrating fields. At least, not without direct reconstruction of the aberrating fields. However, this is not always possible or practical as multiple micrographs taken at different positions are often required to characterise aberrations. Nevertheless, it is known that the human neural network; a network whose intelligence can be be recreated using a neural network no more than about 10 layers deep, is capable of performing this commensuration. Convolutional neural network architecture similar to that used to restyle artwork has therefore been trained to perform this commensuration.

The first 11 layers of VGG-16[20], a 16 layer neural network trained for the 2014 ImageNet[21] image

Figure 3: Registration of fig. 1a with itself and its symmetry space. a) Pearson normalised product moment correlation calculated by padding the image, convolving it with the unpadded image kernel in the Fourier domain and then performing a linear mapping to correct for its edges being padded. Correlation maxima are seen in the center where the images are aligned and at shifts where the spots are overlapping. There are also high peaks at the edges where similar small regions of low-intensity background overlap. b) Sum of squared differences (SSDs) calculated in the Fourier domain similar to a) and normalised by dividing by numbers of overlapping pixels. Minima in b) are seen in the same locations as maxima in a); however, differences are less obvious for peripheral registrations as SSDs are small for differences between the lower intensities at the images' edges. c) Sum of perpendicular gradient filtrates in the largest squares centered on each pixel that fit in the image. Minima estimate locations of maximum global square symmetry. Sums of gradients at the edges are low because the largest squares are smaller and because features are less gradiated at the lower-intensity image peripheries.

classification competition using millions of images, has been attached to a loss network that weights the minimisation of the differences between the micrograph it synthesises and content and style micrographs. The VGG neural network stem is used as a feature extractor. This is an example of transfer learning: part of a neural network trained to perform a one task has being repurposed to perform another. Micrograph synthesis is adjusted to minimise the output of the loss network, which weights the sum of the sum of squared differences between the Gram matrices of the synthesised image and the style image and the sum of squared differences between the content of the synthesised image and the content image. Additionally, the sum of squared differences between adjacent pixels are summed to penalise large differences between adjacent pixels. This helps to prevent the network from synthesising noisy artifacts, albeit at the cost of blurring high frequency components.

At the time of writing, the loss network only minimises differences between the synthesised image and 1 content and 1 style image as it was initially only intended commensurate the style of image with simulations' so that they can more easily be compared. Nevertheless, an arbitrary number of additional loss terms; and therefore images, can be added to the loss network without needing to retrain the network. It is noted that the effect of the synthesised neighboring pixel sum of squared differences loss term can be compensated for using an additional convolutional neural network, similar to the deconvolution network recently developed to decompress images compressed by an embedding convolutional neural network[22], as it is independent of the other loss network contributions.

Task: D-LACBED pattern symmetry determination

Skills: Fourier analysis, Template matching, Overconstrained system of simultaneous equations

Description: The symmetries of patterns mapped out by LACBED pattern disks differs fall into 31 groups depending on crystal symmetry; 21 groups if 2-dimensional (2D) diffraction patterns are discarded. However, the detection of these symmetries is complicated by aberrating fields, radial distortions introduced by diffraction pattern stereography and gaps between disks used to construct the D-LACBED k-space surveys. Moreover, the k-space symmetry center is generally different to survey centers. The approach was therefore

to:

1. Infill gaps using isophote-preserving Navier-Stokes[23] equations.
2. Detect the symmetry center and symmetry group of the central LACBED disk survey by performing combinations of rotations and reflections and registering them against the original image. The central k-space survey always has higher symmetry than the outer k-space surveys so this also gives information about the symmetry group of the D-LACBED pattern.
3. Perform combinations of rotations and reflections on the outer k-space surveys, using the symmetry center of the central survey to estimate their outer k-space survey symmetry centers to constrain their registrations against themselves and other outer k-space surveys. For symmetry groups that don't have outer survey symmetry centers, there are still pseudo-symmetry centers that would be full symmetry centers in the absence of HOLZ lines that can be detected.
4. The symmetry group can be deduced from the symmetries in and between outer k-space surveys
5. Symmetry center positions are affected by aberrating fields so they can be used to estimate them if there are enough k-space surveys to provide the needed degrees of freedom. However, the registrations are unreliable as they are complicated by the distortion fields and dynamical diffraction effect decoupled LACBED disk profiling (a phenomenon I discovered). A procedure based on manifold reconstruction; an unsupervised deep learning technique, is therefore being developed to identify the distortion fields more accurately.

Fourier domain registration using phase correlation or sums of squared differences is not reliable due to periodic intensity undulations caused by the dynamical diffraction effect decoupled disk profile curvature and other aberrations. The best non-feature based detection method was therefore found to be using a product/division of sum of squared differences, Pearson product moment correlation and product gradient moment spaces.

Task: C++ operated MATLAB engine

Skills: Overconstrained systems of simultaneous equations

Description: Most of the work I did on D-LACBED patterns has been written in C++ as DigitalMicroph[24]; a program used for electron micrograph analysis, plugins are most easily interacted with in this language. However, C++ libraries are a much bigger hassle for non-programmers to set up as; unlike a language like python that often has convenient wheels[25], compiler and linker directories have to be configured. I therefore started transferring code to MATLAB to reduce external dependencies; particularly code written using Eigen: a matrix manipulation library. MATLAB functionality is also much easier to program as there are more scientific and statistical tools available. In particular, a trust-region[26] algorithm needed to solve an overconstrained system of non-linear simultaneous equations to fit a monotonically decreasing cubic Bezier[27] surface of revolution to a dynamical diffraction effect decoupled LACBED disk profiles.

Task: Ellipse fitting by hyper-renormalisation[28]

Skills: Overconstrained system of simultaneous equations

Description: D-LACBED k-space survey symmetry centers can be used to construct the distorting field; however, these only offer a similar number of degrees of freedom to the minimum needed to construct the aberrating fields and may not be very accurate. An alternative approach is to directly measure how the LACBED disk lattice is distorted as it moves through the aberrating field by measuring the positions of the disks. This offers far more degrees of freedom; however, the exact positions are difficult to measure as they are often obscured by dynamical diffraction effects. The following procedure was therefore implemented:

1. Extract regions of interest from LACBED micrographs where disks are known to be that are slightly larger than the approximate sizes of the disks (the disk positions and sizes are likely slightly off)
2. Calculate the amplitude of the region's Scharr filtrate. The edges of the disk are revealed by high Scharr filtrate values

3. Use k-means clustering to threshold and binarise the high Scharr filtrate values
4. Use hyper-renormalisation to fit a conic section to the binarised points, weighting it using pixel brightnesses. The ellipse parameters can then be extracted by rotating the conic section
5. Calculate the weighted median distance from the ellipse
6. Fit an ellipse to the pixels within 1.0 weighted median distance from the ellipse fitted by the first hyper-renormalisation, weighting them by their brightnesses.
7. Extract the ellipse from the conic section of the second hyper-renormalisation

Hyper-renormalisation followed by median-based outlier removal and a second hyper-renormalisation are all that is needed to accurately fit ellipses in practice. Nevertheless, additional outlier removal and hyper-renormalisation cycles can be performed until the solution converges, if necessary. However, it is cautioned that the additional accuracy is unlikely to be useful: it is only as useful as the disk's Scharr filtrate is as a measure of its shape. 12 different ellipse fitting algorithms and modifications that could be made to them were considered. Perhaps surprising, the 4 ellipse-specific algorithms that were considered were the least reliable: they tend to produce ellipses that are either way too small or a bit too large. This is why the ellipse was fitted using a conic sections. The main contenders were FNS with the hyper-accurate correction or hyper-renormalisation, which produce very similar results. Hyper-renormalisation was chosen because it is rumored to be the better approach on statistics forums.

Task: Low electron dose EELS[29] image stack compression

Skills: Data compression

Description: A data-specific lossless data compression algorithm has been developed to compress low-dose EELS image stacks. These contain sparsities of non-zero elements that can be lower than 0.01% and can therefore be compressed very efficiently using a data-specific algorithm:

1. Flatten the 3D image stack into a 1D array so that each position can be represented by a single number, rather than 3. The 1D positions can be mapped back onto their 3D positions later by storing the number of rows, columns and images in the compressed data file
2. Interleave relative positions and values of non-zero pixels into a 1D array. If y is the ratio of the file size to the original and x is the sparsity of non-zero elements, this reduces the ratio to $y = 2x$: a factor of 5000 reduction in dataset size for $x = 0.01\%$. Relative positions are used to avoid problems caused by positions numbers becoming larger than the maximum size of 32 bit integers and to keep the position numbers as small as possible so that they can be more efficiently compressed.
3. Electron counts and relative positions are small so the unsigned integers can be compressed by at least a factor of 5 using a C# Fibonacci codec[30]. This codec was chosen as it has the best compression ratio for numbers smaller than 8000 whilst still having reasonable performance for larger numbers in cases where electron counts are particularly high. Compression by a factor of 5 reduces reduces the size to $y = (2/5)x = 0.4x$.
4. The file size can then be reduced further using a standard compression codec. Zip compression, given sufficient system resources and compression time, can typically reduce large file sizes to less than a third of their original size[31, 32], giving a ratio less than $y = 0.15x$. This is a lossless data size reduction of over 66000 times for $x = 0.01\%$.

Task: LACBED dynamical diffraction effect decoupled disk profiling

Skills: Overconstrained system of simultaneous equations

Description: LACBED disks can be decoupled from dynamic diffraction effects by calculating the ratios of pixels where 2 disks overlap as the dynamical diffraction patterns are expected to be the same where the disks overlap. The ratios for various distances from the spot centers can then be used to fit an overconstrained system of ratios of monotonically decreasing cubic Bezier curves using a trust-region algorithm. By assuming

Figure 4: a) and b) show part of a LACBED pattern of an unknown material at different tilts. c) shows the Hadamard division of a) and b) where smaller pixels are divided by the larger. In the absence of dynamical diffraction effect decoupled LACBED disk profile curvature, the ratios where the disks overlap is expected to be uniform. However, careful inspection reveals that ratios decrease with pixel distance from disk centers. d) The non-black pixels show a cubic monotonically decreasing Bezier surface of revolution fitted to dynamical diffraction effect decoupled LACBED disk profiles by solving an overconstrained system of ratios of cubic Bezier curves using a trust-region algorithm[26].

that the dynamical diffraction effect decoupled LACBED disk profiles are symmetric about their centres, a surface of revolution can be generated to model and adjust the disk profile intensities when creating k-space surveys.

Note that it is not yet clear that this effect isn't anomalous. Its presence has only been studied in 3 D-LACBED stacks: it appears to be present in 2 D-LACBED image stacks that where the disks are small; however, it does not appear to be significant in a large disk diffraction pattern. A quantitative study needs to be performed using a larger number of image stacks to decide what the effect is conclusively. Nevertheless, if this profiling effect is present, the profile may be more readily constructed using manifold reconstruction[33–35] in the future: the neural network can be instructed to train itself until its learning curve plateaus.

Task: C++ image stack reader

Skills: Know when to look through repositories for code that has already been written

Description: Rather than writing an image reader that strips buffering bytes to extract image files, I searched through various code repositories until I found one. The OpenCV 3.3 C++ library has a function to do this. However, OpenCV 3.3's python wrapper does not.

Figure 5: Each column shows $200\text{px}\times 200\text{px}$ artwork generated from randomly initialised simple neural networks with different activation functions. The neural networks used to produce this art have less than 30 neurons in their layers so that their outputs are spatially correlated. Rows show that artwork generated from the same neural network with different random initialisations has a similar style; characteristic of that network’s activation functions. Source code is referenced: [39].

Regardless, it is noted that if one needs to design a image stack reader for an unusual image stack format, MATLAB’s `fread()`[36] may make this particularly easy. It has inbuilt byte-skipping capabilities and the readout format is easily specified. However, if speed matters it is probably better to write it in a compiled language such as C++. I recommend C#; a language mainly used for interfacing, as it has particularly easy-to-use streams[37]. Unlike C++, it has native garbage collection.

Task: Navier-Stokes infilling

Skills: Image enhancement

Description: Before starting to use convolutional neural networks for noise removal and data enhancement, the Navier-Stokes equations were used. For instance, dead pixels or x-ray spikes (salt and pepper noise) can be identified using differences of Gaussians and then infilled using the Navier-Stokes equations. Taking this to an extreme, I trailed functionality that replaced each pixel with the Navier-Stokes inflow from its neighbors. This is effective; however, it isn’t competitive with bilateral filtering[38] or deep learning-based approaches. Nevertheless, it might have a higher performance for images with low gradation. Navier-Stokes infilling is also being used to infill LACBED disks from the surrounding diffuse electron background so that it can be subtracted; however, it is noted that such subtraction is questionable regardless of the method used as dynamical diffraction effect patterns can extend from LACBED disks into the supposedly diffuse surrounding background.

Task: Artistic neural networks

Skills: Neural networks

Description: A neural network that is initialised with a random collection of weights and biases will produce artwork with a style that is characterised by its activation functions. If this neural network has 2 inputs and 1 output then it acts as a function that can create a greyscale image from pixel positions. However, provided that the number of neurons is reasonably low, the outputs for pixels with similar locations are likely to be locally correlated, resulting in a pattern that looks like modern art. This type of neural network is useful as the artwork they produce contains features that can be corrupted; for instance, by Poisson noise and used to train other neural networks that are being prototyped. If this initial training is successful, data can then be acquired by experiment or from the electron microscopy data servers for more comprehensive training.

Task: Noise residual synthesis

Skills: Convolutional neural networks

Description: Recent papers have demonstrated that convolutional architecture can be used to remove salt and pepper noise from images with superior performance to more traditional filter kernels. However, the architectures I have seen are typically trained on small images; often 32 by 32, and directly reconstruct the output image. This is in contrast to the approach used in recent paper on the use of a deconvolutional neural network to decompress images compressed using another convolutional neural network. Rather than reconstructing the original image, it constructed residuals to add to the original image. This allowed the more effective use of batch normalisation between convolutions to speed up training time. Neural networks are therefore being developed using this approach to enhance images created by a style transfer neural network and to enhance images corrupted by Poisson noise.

Task: DMScript marionette

Skills: Electron microscope interface, Asynchronous processes, Neural network control

Description: Rather than compiling C++ Digital micrograph plugins; which is a hassle as they have to be compiled with a 2008 C++ compiler, a marionette has been DMScripted to allow an electron microscope to be remote controlled by exchanging instruction and data files via an electron microscopy network drive. A python interface has been developed to asynchronously control the marionette; however, the marionette could be communicated with using instruction files written in any language. This interface was designed to enable electron microscopes to be remote-controlled by neural networks optimising Markov decision processes.

Task: Feature size estimation

Skills: Fourier analysis, Regulating neural network

Description: The feature size distribution in an image can be characterised by calculating its 2D Fourier transform, converting it to a 1D spectrum by summing frequency components in quadrature and then calculating its moments. This may appear questionable as frequencies are summed rather periods. However, it is not possible to meaningfully characterise size distributions using all the periods as the zero frequency components would be inverted to infinite periods. Additionally, divisions take tens of times longer than other operations on most CPUs and start to become expensive if this procedure has to be applied many times. Moreover, any nonlinearities introduced by summing frequencies in quadrature will be understood by the non-linear activation functions of a neural network using them.

The procedure has already been implemented with the intention to use these and other moments to train a simple neural network e.g. with 2 hidden layers of Sigmoidal neurons. These can be concatenated with other information; such as the characterisation of micrograph noise using differences of 1x1 and 3x3 Gaussians, to predict the optimal parameters to use when adjusting images with a style transfer neural network.

Task: Gradient product transform[40] symmetry detection

Skills: Statistical analysis, Symmetry detection

Description: A novel, non-feature based Linux symmetry detection library has been hacked so that it can be used functionally via a C++ dynamic link library. This has been published in one my GitHub repositories along with the author's original license[41]. It was hoped that this library could be used to predict the symmetry centers of D-LACBED k-space surveys. It can; however, it is also much slower than feature-based methods. Nevertheless, the novel approach being used could be adjusted and implemented much more quickly as the symmetry being searched for are known as well as their scale: global. This approach has been

combined with other approaches to weight symmetry detection in D-LACBED k-space surveys.

3 Specialist Skills

I have learned to use a range of specialist computer vision, deep learning, GPU acceleration and other libraries, including:

- OpenCV[2]: Computer vision
- OpenCL[7]: GPU acceleration
- ArrayFire[8]: High-level GPU acceleration
- Eigen[42]: Matrix manipulation
- Integer-Compression[30] and TurboPFor[43]: Integer compression codecs
- Keras[44]: High-level deep learning framework
- TensorFlow[45]: Keras backend and tensor manipulation library
- Theano[46]: Keras backend and tensor manipulation library
- FFTW3[47]: Fastest Fourier transform in the west
- clFFT[48]: Bakeable GPU-accelerated Fourier transforms
- OpenMP[5]: Multithreading
- Arduino[49]: Microcontrollers
- OpenAI Gym[50]: Neural network-environment interfacing

A range of programming languages are being used as appropriate for different tasks. Different languages have different strengths and weaknesses:

- A specialised programming library that is needed to perform a task may only be available in a particular language. For example, most low-level GPU acceleration and multithreading libraries are designed to be used in C++. Parallelism in interpreted or higher-level environments; such as Mathematica, tends to be higher-level and not offer as fine control.
- A language may be fast to prototype in because a lot of task-specific functionality is readily available. For instance, MATLAB has a lot of easy-to-use mathematical tools for matrix manipulation and optimisation. However, it is also slow and the MATLAB engine often has to be used to run MATLAB code from other languages as C++ conversion of functionality containing specialised functions often isn't supported.
- Some language are easier for others with less programming experience to maintain or build upon. For instance, python is very simple and most libraries can be installed via easy-to-use wheels. Juxtapositionally, C++ is complicated by headers and external libraries have to be explicitly included and linked to.

At the moment I'm using C, C++, C#, python, MATLAB and Mathematica; however, I can program in dozens of languages and will likely use other languages for new tasks in the future. For instance, I may do some work with some D-LACBED k-space survey simulations written in FORTRAN.

4 MPAGS modules and Doctoral Skills

I have completed the following MPAGS modules:

- PX904: Properties and Characterisation of Materials (2 credits)
- PX905: Defects and Dopants (2 credits)
- CH978: Surfaces, Interfaces and Coatings (2 credits)

I have completed the following Doctoral Skills Year 1 tasks:

- Teaching and Demonstrating Training
- Pass "Equality and Diversity Training" Course Assignment
- Pass "Anti-Plagiarism" Course Assignment
- Project Risk Analysis Assignment
- Submit Project Outline Assignment

5 PhD 2 Year Outline

Hologram reconstruction: UCLA researchers have recently demonstrated that GPU-accelerated deep convolutional neural networks can reconstruct optical microscopic holograms more efficiently than traditional GPU-accelerated hologram reconstruction algorithms[51]. Electron microscopic focal series are therefore being collected to reconstruct electron microscopic holograms from[52]. These will be used to train a deep convolutional neural network that has been developed to apply the UCLA researchers' success to electron microscopy.

Semantic segmentation: Google's breakthrough application of an atrous convolutional spatial pyramid pooling neural network to semantic image segmentation[53] is being applied to electron microscopy. Confusing convolutions will be applied to generalise the neural network to multiple imaging conditions[54]. Deep reinforcement learning networks[50, 55, 56] will then be built to utilise the semantic segmentation in a move towards driverless electron microscopy.

Position location: Compressed sensing[57] of an atrous convolutional spatial pyramid pooling neural network will be applied to the live inference of atom positions and their displacements. This will be used study materials' atomic structure and to study the statistics of atom motion in an electron beam.

Style transfer: Tensors from a feature-extracting convolutional neural network trained on millions of images can be flowed into a loss network that synthesizes a micrograph with features most commensurate with the input micrographs'. This can be used cosmetically to restyle a micrograph with another; for instance, by minimising differences between Gram matrices[58], similar to the approach used when creating neural network art[59]. More ambitiously, semantic segmentation can be used when evaluating the loss function to directly imbue micrographs with characteristics of simulations or vice versa without introducing large local distortions[60].

Noise removal: Convolutional architectures have been developed to remove Gaussian[61, 62], speckle[62, 63] and salt and pepper noise[62]. However, many of these networks directly reconstruct enhanced images and do not use batch normalization inbetween convolutions to speed up training. If a network is trained to output residuals to add to an input micrograph to enhance it; rather than directly reconstructing the enhanced micrograph, it may be possible to use batch normalisation inbetween convolutions, similar to the approach recently used to train a novel decompressing convolutional neural network[22]. Alternatively, residual connections could be introduced[64]. It is thought that an alternative architecture will allow larger noise-removing architectures to train more quickly, enabling the convolution of larger feature spaces and thus enhancing their ability to characterise noise.

Micrograph stack compression: A novel compression framework that uses dual convolutional neural networks alongside traditional codecs has recently been developed for 2D images[22]. A similar architecture is being developed to compress 3-dimensional (3D) micrograph stacks that works alongside traditional micrograph stack compression codecs. The added benefit is that 3D convolutions can be used to extract features, imbuing the architecture with knowledge of a 3rd dimension of correlations and therefore reducing the number of convolutional layers that would otherwise need to be trained.

Manifold reconstruction: This is a machine learning technique used to find a low-dimensional mapping between a source and target domain[33–35, 65]. After the neural network is trained, it projects points from the source domain onto a manifold; characterising the relationship between the source and target domain. This can be used to efficiently generate dynamical diffraction effect decoupled LACBED disk profiles. The network can be regularised to ensure that it generates smooth profiles.

Material classification: Some materials or phases of materials are difficult to classify. However, trained state-of-the-art deep learning architectures; such as Inception[66], Inception-ResNet[17] and VGG-16[20], are publicly available[67] and their final layers can be retrained[15] to perform these difficult classifications, especially with the help of a support vector machine[68, 69] or via all-transfer learning[70].

6 Key Text Reviews

6.1 A computational Introduction to Digital Image Processing

Reference [12]: *A. McAndrew, A computational Introduction to Digital Image Processing, 2nd Edition, CRC Press, 2016.*

This introductory image processing textbook gives a clear, concise description of how to use various image processing techniques. It is aimed at those with some programming experience; however, it doesn't make assumptions about the nature of that experience or the reader's mathematical background. It therefore only presents theory behind image processing techniques when not doing so can be a source of confusion and does so from a programmer's perspective. For instance, when covering fast Fourier transforms, the author describes the Fourier butterfly and some useful image processing relations such as the convolution theorem; however, the author does not go into any non-algorithmic mathematical detail or discuss anything that does not frequently have applications in image processing.

Most of the book is code-focused: image processing techniques are introduced alongside code that puts them into practice and the results of that code. Code is provided in python, MATLAB and Octave, making it accessible to a wider range of readers than it might be otherwise. Most new programmers learn either python or MATLAB at some point and will likely have learned one of these languages before starting to work in image processing. I like how code is also presented in Octave; a free, less complete version of MATLAB, for those who may not be able to afford or do not currently have access to MATLAB.

The strength of this book is its focus on how to use image processing techniques. It makes it useful to programmers working in any language and is why I was able to usefully refer to it when implementing low/high pass filters, performing morphological operations and manipulating image histograms in C++. However, this is also its greatest weakness: it only focuses on the application of computational techniques, rather than the best ways to apply them. This means that it makes little to no reference to GPU-acceleration, multithreading or the efficient implementation of algorithms. For instance, the book introduces Fourier-domain convolutions; however, it does not state that these are most appropriate for kernels at least about 11×11 in size (depending on the size of the image the kernel is being convolved with).

Although the book avoids discussing advanced computational methods such as GPU acceleration, it does go into considerable detail about image-specific topics that are accessible to most programmers. For instance, it details the different image file types; such as .png, .jpeg and .tiff, both explaining the advantages and disadvantages of the different formats as well as the structure of the data in image files. This information is particularly useful to newer programmers who may not have otherwise had any reason to think about the different file types: most computers/software now come with codecs that can interpret most common image file types.

6.2 Advances in Computational Methods for Transmission Electron Microscopy Simulation and Image Processing

Reference [10]: *M. A. Dyson, PhD thesis, Advances in Computational Methods for Transmission Electron Microscopy Simulation and Image Processing, University of Warwick, 2014.*

This thesis focuses on exit wave reconstruction; however, to me it is most notable for its description of GPU-accelerated multislice simulations. Indeed, it is the first text I read on GPU-accelerated Fourier analysis. Having worked in computer vision for several months, perhaps the most useful takeaway is the author's pragmatic use of brute-force. For instance, when template matching to align images in an image stack, he brute-forced the cross-correlation of all the possible registrations within some radius. At first, I was taken aback by this as I reasoned that it would surely be better to implement a few thousand calculations in an a maximum-finding procedure rather than the hundreds of thousands of calculations needed to brute-force the calculations. However, this thinking is naive: GPUs are very good at the highly parallelisable brute-force calculations and terrible at the serial calculations typically required in optimization algorithms. Unlike CPUs, GPUs are not optimised for serial calculations; they are optimised to perform many calculations in parallel.

The author’s pragmatic use of brute-force is particularly appropriate when GPU-accelerating Fourier analysis. Rather than caching and applying a window function to break cyclicity, he padded micrographs with zeros. This is particularly sensible for scientific applications as spectral leakage from window functions can introduce unwanted artifacts. This does increase the number calculations by a factor of 4; however, these calculations are highly parallelisable and are therefore readily handled by a GPU. As the calculations were sensitive, I think this trade was worth it for the freedom from artifacts.

The author’s use of heterogeneous computing is particularly remarkable. At the time of writing, the only architectures in common use were the CPU, for serial calculations, and the GPU, which was being incepted; driven by Apple’s successful development of OpenCL, to perform highly parallelised calculations. High-level GPU-acceleration libraries were not as developed or readily available so kernels had to be written using low-level OpenCL or CUDA regardless of their simplicity. GPUs were just starting to be popularly used for intensive calculations, partly driven by the development of increasingly elaborate architectures for cryptocurrency mining and increasing demand for 3D graphics rendering.

Applying the author’s success with heterogeneous architecture to new architectures being developed today, it is noted that Google recently announced the development of a cloud tensor processing unit[71] (TPU) platform for machine learning[72]. Field programmable gate arrays (FPGAs) are also being configured to outperform GPU-based neural network acceleration[73]. This is interesting as the recent development of OpenCL-compatible FPGAs by Alterra[74] may mean that it will soon be practical to use them to run neural networks. FPGAs may be better at modeling less-layered, more biological architectures as bitstreams that dedicate the architecture to the specific neural network can be synthesised. Consequently, I learned some Verilog[75]; a hardware description language, and practiced FPGA bitstream synthesis in my own time in case it is useful for this in the future. The drawback is that complicated bitstreams can take hours to synthesize and test, unlike kernels launched on CPUs or GPUs.

6.3 Advanced Computing in Electron Microscopy

Reference [11]: E. J. Kirkland, *Advanced Computing in Electron Microscopy, 2nd Edition*, Springer, 2010.

This book is on established computational methods in electron microscopy. It gives an especially detailed description of multislice simulations: a popular method used to simulate materials. Indeed, GPU-accelerated multislice simulations are the subject of Dyson’s thesis[10]; one of the other key texts I summarize. This book is especially helpful because it presents equations and techniques from a programmer’s perspective; so that the transition from equations to practice is obvious. For instance, when introducing series used to describe aberrating fields, the author carefully describes the full derivation and makes it clear how to computationally apply them to images. This is particularly helpful as these equations are normally only stated in passing, as in reference [76] and reference [77].

The book also helpfully describes the rearrangement of fast Fourier transform quadrants, similar to reference [12], so that the low frequency components are at the center. However, the book is limited to theoretical descriptions and doesn’t give key practical insights. For instance, when performing Fourier transforms of real data, almost half of the Fourier components are complex conjugates of those in other quadrants and therefore have Hermitian redundancy. Good Fourier transform libraries; including ArrayFire, FFTW3 and cFFFT, offer real to complex Fourier transforms that do not perform the unnecessary calculations of these redundant components, decreasing the number of calculations and memory required. Most of my Fourier transforms of real data are performed this way. Note; however, that this can be a bit fiddly when performing an in-place Fourier transform in locked allocated memory as the real data has to be padded so that there is enough space for interleaved components of the Fourier transform.

The use of multislice simulations to simulate a range of image types is described; including the use of one multislice simulation to simulate CBED images. Helpfully, it describes the setup for simulations in considerable detail, providing examples of simulations for different parameters and concisely describes special conditions needed to generate the simulations. It even describes variants of similar simulations such as CBED and LACBED with examples.

Some source code is provided for the simulations; however, this is all provided in C or FORTRAN. This makes sense as these languages are designed for numerical calculation; however, higher-level languages now support a lot of functionality written in lower-level, compiled languages so it is no longer as necessary to

write out numerical routines. A good example of such a high-level library is python's numpy which mainly consists of wrappers for low-level C code. That's why you don't don't experience a significant speed increase when using numpy on small datasets: there are wrapper overheads. If functionality is missing and isn't available in SciPy[78] or other libraries, it has a C application programming interface [79] that can be used to extend it. This means that easy-to-use python can be used to write most functionality quickly and used to wrap low-level C code when it needs to be written to remove numerical bottlenecks. BOOST.Python[80] can also be used and is designed for C++; however, it is aimed at experienced programmers and can be difficult to set up.

6.4 Transmission Electron Microscopy: Diffraction, Imaging and Spectrometry

Reference [76]: C. B. Carter and D. B. Williams, *Transmission Electron Microscopy: Diffraction, Imaging and Spectrometry*, Springer, 2016.

This book covers most aspects of modern electron microscopy, including the use of Gatan's DMScript[81] language in their DigitalMicrograph software. However, I have found it to be insufficiently in-depth. For examples, it doesn't go into much detail about the computation of aberrating fields like reference [11] and doesn't add anything significant in its DMScript description that isn't available in its programming documentation or publicly available source code. References are provided throughout the book, so I think it is a good starting point when learning about something as it covers almost everything; however, it is not sufficiently in-depth to be of much use beyond that. It doesn't help that DMScript, the language covered in the book, is interpreted, so intensive numerical methods have to be developed in other languages that can be compiled for speed and then plugged in to DigitalMicrograph.

Nevertheless, chapter 6 does have a useful section on developing DigitalMicrograph user interfaces and adding metadata to images with DMScript. As this is a rather esoteric language, it is difficult to find good documentation (the Digital Micrograph documentation doesn't have examples) outside of others' source code. However, this chapter provides some documentation, with examples of some of the more basic operations such as adding tags containing information to DigitalMicrograph images and basic images handling commands like slicing, separating real and imaginary parts, selecting regions of interest and so on. Unfortunately, it doesn't cover how to build DigitalMicrograph C++ plugins and I had to find a dedicated guide[82] for that. This is a surprisingly difficult procedure: to build them in Visual Studio 2017 you need the Visual Studio 2008 toolkit; to use this you need the Visual Studio 2010 toolkit; to use this you also need the 2012 development tools. If this isn't bad enough, the 2008 and 2010 toolkits are no longer officially (at least, straightforwardly) distributed by Microsoft. Specific versions of BOOST and DigitalMicrograph development kits also have to be configured. One way to avoid this esoteric setup is to set up a virtual machine for electron microscopists to develop plugins with, snapshotting it to avoid expiration issues. I've developed on an alternative solution where the electron microscope can be remote controlled through an intermediate buffer using instruction files written in any language.

The other focus of this book; outside of methods used to study materials, is the physics of the electron microscope itself. The first chapter details electron sources and electron optics are described and depicted in other chapters where methods are introduced. I have also found our JEOL 2100 electron microscope manual to be a helpful aid as it contains diagrams and details of the specific microscope we are using at Warwick. I have found the most useful diagrams and descriptions to be those in chapter 4 as this is on the CBED patterns that I have spent some time working with.

6.5 Heterogeneous Computing with OpenCL

Reference [4]: B. R. Gaster, *Heterogeneous Computing with OpenCL, 2nd Edition*, Elsevier/Morgan Kaufmann, 2013.

This textbook starts by introducing the state of heterogeneous architecture and the tradeoffs associated with using different types of architecture and memory caches. Specifically, the focus of the first 2 chapters is on the physical architecture of computer chips, how this effects computation and the types of instructions and scheduling used by memory managers to ensure efficient calculation. From chapter 3, OpenCL kernels

and their outputs are presented to demonstrate how to efficiently schedule calculations and use various memory caches. Since OpenCL is mainly used for GPU acceleration, this is inexorably the focus of the book. Nevertheless, kernels are presented from a device- and platform-independent standpoint as they can be launched on any device conforming to the OpenCL specification[83].

OpenCL was originally developed by Apple to program heterogeneous computational architecture using C-style kernels. The OpenCL standard is now maintained by the non-profit Khronos Consortium and is implemented by a huge range of corporations[7], including AMD, IBM and Altera. OpenCL is designed to be architecture independent. However, in practice OpenCL is mainly a low-level GPU acceleration library whose kernels can run on CPUs if a GPU isn't available. My main use for OpenCL has been the production of GPU-side convolution kernels and algorithms that are outside the scope of the higher-level ArrayFire C++ application programming interface (API) that I used to GPU-accelerate Fourier-domain convolutions to extract features from large LACBED image stacks. This is possible because ArrayFire has inbuilt ArrayFire-OpenCL interoperability. ArrayFire also supports interoperability with CUDA[84], another popular GPU-acceleration backend.

The main difficulty I had when learning OpenCL from this book was caused by example code being written in multiple versions of OpenCL, or at least not being compatible with the version I am using: OpenCL 2.0. This is because some common OpenCL command names changed between versions and the original commands became deprecated[85]. There is a simple fix: `#define CL_USE_DEPRECATED_OPENCL_2_0_APIS` to disable depreciation. It also helps to `#define __CL_ENABLE_EXCEPTIONS` in case something goes wrong.

The only other complication was the construction of platform-specific kernel launchers. OpenCL is designed to be platform independent so these are not packaged with its distributions. Perhaps surprisingly, in most of the source code I worked through when learning OpenCL, programmers chose to explicitly construct and launch kernels mid-code rather than writing functions that could repeatedly be reused. Indeed, one of the first things I did when GPU-accelerating LACBED feature extraction was to write a kernel constructor. I also created kernel-launching functions for my kernels so that I could easily reuse them.

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